

Moderate Dispositional Structuralism

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Abstract. Dispositionalism holds that at least some fundamental physical properties are ungrounded dispositional ones. Unfortunately, the very scientific practice that dispositionalists invoke to support their view undermines the dispositional thesis: putative fundamental properties such as *mass*, *charge*, and *spin* appear to be grounded in symmetry structures. Can the dispositionalist hold that fundamental symmetry structures are dispositional? Livanios (2019) defends a negative answer: symmetry structures do not satisfy the truthmaking principle of dispositionality. By contrast, I offer a positive answer. Here I argue that if dispositionalists adopt an *identity-based criterion* of dispositionality, they can endorse what I shall call *moderate dispositional structuralism*: the view that the identity of fundamental symmetry structures is partially but not exhaustively fixed by their dispositional character. The purpose of this paper is to articulate moderate dispositional structuralism and its merits. To defend the plausibility of this view, I compare it with its radical counterpart: the view that the identity of symmetry structures is fully or wholly fixed by their dispositionality.

Resumen. El disposicionalismo sostiene que al menos algunas propiedades físicas fundamentales son disposicionales sin fundamento. Desafortunadamente, la misma práctica científica que los disposicionalistas invocan para apoyar su punto de vista socava la tesis disposicional: las supuestas propiedades fundamentales como la masa, la carga y el espín parecen estar fundamentadas en estructuras de simetría. ¿Puede el disposicionalista sostener que las estructuras de simetría fundamentales son disposicionales? Livanios (2019) defiende una respuesta negativa: las estructuras de simetría no satisfacen el principio de verdad de la disposicionalidad. Por el contrario, yo ofrezco una respuesta positiva. Aquí sostengo que si los disposicionalistas adoptan un criterio de disposicionalidad basado en la identidad, pueden respaldar lo que llamaré estructuralismo

disposicional moderado: la visión de que la identidad de las estructuras de simetría fundamentales está parcialmente, pero no exhaustivamente, determinada por su carácter disposicional. El propósito de este artículo es articular el estructuralismo disposicional moderado y sus méritos. Para defender la plausibilidad de esta visión, la comparo con su contraparte radical: la visión de que la identidad de las estructuras de simetría está total o completamente determinada por su disposicionalidad.

1. Fundamentally Dispositional

Among other things, metaphysicians of sciences aspire to give a scientifically-informed account of the *ontological type* of the most fundamental features (properties or relations) of our world. Two monistic views defend rival positions. On *categoricalism*, the fundamental properties and relations are essentially categorical or qualitative. On *dispositionalism*, these are essentially dispositional or powerful.

To spell out the clash between these views, we need to clarify the *categorical–dispositional distinction*. As it happens, this is not an easy task. On a popular view, the distinction between the categorical and the dispositional is mutually exclusive: categorical properties (or relations) are non-dispositional.

What is it for something to be dispositional? At heart, dispositionality is a matter of how a thing is disposed to behave in various possible circumstances in virtue of having certain features. It is orthodoxy amongst the dispositionalists to endorse an *identity-based criterion* of dispositionality that states that a feature is dispositional just in case its identity is at least partially fixed by its causal/dispositional/nomic role. The latter involves the causal/dispositional/nomic relations that the feature in question has to other ones (Shoemaker 1980; Molnar 2003; Mumford 2004; Bird 2007, 2016; Engelhard 2010).¹ Call this ‘dispositional character’ for short. Typically, specifications of the

¹ On some views, the dispositional character of a feature flows from its essence (Swoyer 1982; Ellis and Lierse 1994; Bird 2007; Bauer 2013; Yates 2013). That is, the essence of a dispositional features comprises a certain dispositional character. This characterisation ensures the modal fixity of dispositional features.

dispositional character involve overt or covert dispositional terms and are often expressed by subjunctive conditionals that refer to characteristic manifestations in distinctive circumstances. Dispositionalists of various stripes agree that the dispositional character is modally fixed: the same dispositional feature cannot have a different dispositional character in other possible worlds. Its dispositional character is necessary. To illustrate this position, let us consider a familiar example of a dispositional property such as *fragility*. Dispositionalists maintain that *fragility* is dispositional because its identity is at least partially fixed by the disposition to shatter in some circumstances that fragile things have in virtue of instantiating this property. Given the modal fixity of dispositional character, in every possible world, fragile objects are disposed to shatter in certain circumstances.

If we think of the categorical as the non-dispositional, then categorical features are those whose identity is not fixed by their dispositional character. Said differently, the identity of categorical features is independent from the causal/dispositional/nomic role they play. This characterisation has an important modal implication: a categorical property can vary its dispositional character across possible world. Classic albeit controversial examples of categorical properties include structural properties (*having a tetrahedral molecular arrangement*), geometrical properties (*having a spherical shape*), and quantitative properties (*having a determinate volume*). The categoricist does not deny that these properties are tied to some causal/nomic/dispositional roles. But they are not responsible, metaphysically speaking, for the dispositional character they have.² For instance, the categoricist holds that the identity of *having a spherical shape* is not fixed by any dispositions (such as that of rolling on inclined planes). On its own, *having a spherical shape* is a self-contained property that has a primitive identity.³

² The connection between categorical properties and dispositions obtains in virtue of external features to the properties themselves, typically laws of nature (e.g. Armstrong 1997).

³ One worry with this characterisation is that it rules out *by fiat* another monistic view of fundamental properties: the *identity theory of powerful qualities*, which takes the dispositional to be identical with the categorical (e.g. Heil 2003; Martin 2008). Of course, if dispositionality is partially fixed by the dispositional character and categoricity is not, then these cannot be identical. So, the identity theorist

The dispute between categoricalists and dispositionalists is a key battleground in contemporary metaphysics. Categoricalism has a distinctive Humean flavour; dispositionalism is unabashedly anti-Humean. The dispositionalist embraces the idea that the world is fundamentally modally imbued: there are necessary connections between fundamental properties and their dispositional character. The categoricalist rejects this picture.

Here my focus is on dispositionalism. One of the central tenets of this view is that some fundamental dispositional properties such as *mass*, *charge*, and *spin* are *ungrounded* (e.g. Molnar 2003; Mumford 2006). That is, they do not depend on further entities that ground their dispositionality.

The dispositionalist thesis has been often motivated by appealing to scientific practice. Surely, it would be an important advantage for dispositionalists if physics were to support their view. Unfortunately, the very scientific practice that dispositionalists invoke also undermines the tenability of their view. Contemporary physics strongly suggests that fundamental physical properties are grounded in *symmetry structures*, or *groups* (Livanios 2010, 2016; 2019; French 2014). Therefore, these symmetry structures, which are groups of symmetry transformations that can be described mathematically in accordance with group theory, are more fundamental than the claimed fundamental dispositional properties. The dispositionalist thesis is in great peril: if the “fundamental” physical dispositional properties are further grounded in symmetry structures, then the former are neither fundamental nor ungrounded. Call this the *Grounded Argument* against dispositionalism.⁴

ought to conceive the categorical in a different way. Unfortunately, it is not crystal clear in which one (for a critical assessment of the identity theory, see Taylor 2018 and Giannotti forthcoming). My focus in this paper is on dispositionalism. Therefore, I shall not endeavour to provide a characterisation of the dispositional–categorical distinction that accommodates the identity theory.

⁴ One could relativize the fundamentality claim to the category of properties. But this move won’t save the dispositionalist. As I shall explain in the next section, the fact that symmetry structures

In this paper, I make the *Grounded Argument* more precise and show how the dispositionalist can resist it. In doing so, I address the question of whether symmetry structures can be accommodated within a dispositionalist framework, which is a task that has been overlooked in the literature.⁵ Can the dispositionalist hold that fundamental symmetry structures are dispositional? Livanios (2019) defends a negative answer. By contrast, here I argued for a positive answer. I shall articulate and defend the plausibility of an identity-based version of *moderate dispositional structuralism*: the view that the identity of fundamental symmetry structures is partially but not exhaustively fixed by their dispositional character. The moral of this paper is that the dispositionalist can resist the charge that physics undermines the dispositionalist thesis. However, I conclude by pointing out that the prospects of a *radical* version of dispositional structuralism, according to which fundamental symmetry structures are exhaustively dispositional, are rather dim.

I shall proceed as follows. In the remainder of this section, I will lay out a few preliminary remarks and assumptions. In Section 2, I will present the Grounded Argument in more detail and discuss Livanios's version of dispositional structuralism. In Section 3, I will argue in favour of an identity-based version of moderate dispositional structuralism. After outlining the merits of this view, I will conclude by calling into question the plausibility its radical counterpart.

Before discussing the Grounded Argument, I must lay out some assumptions and clarify the notion of a symmetry structure.

To begin with, I assume that symmetry structures are ontic or ontologically robust physical entities that can be analysed mathematically in accordance with group theory. Here I shall not attempt to defend this assumption (for an extensive treatment of arguments and considerations in favour of the reality of fundamental symmetry structures, see Ladyman and Ross 2007 and French

ground putative fundamental properties undermines the claim that these are identified by reference to their dispositional character.

⁵ Livanios (2019) is a notable exception. However, as I will explain in due course, Livanios defends an opposite claim, namely that symmetry structures are not dispositional.

2014; for an overview of ontic structuralist approaches in the philosophy of physics, see Esfeld and Lam 2011 and MacKenzie 2017). Relatedly, I assume that symmetry structures are kinds of entities that can be suitably characterised as either dispositional or categorical (see Livanios 2019 for a defence of this claim). This paper is not meant to persuade those who do not include symmetry structures in the inventory of what there is. Nor is it supposed to convince those who think of symmetry structure cannot be either dispositional or categorical to change their own mind.

Secondly, the novelty of my approach does not lie in the idea of taking structures as dispositional.⁶ Rather it consists in defending a positive argument for a moderate form of dispositional structuralism, one which is articulated from the viewpoint of the identity-based criterion of dispositionality. Therefore, the proposed form of dispositional structuralism should be distinguished from other ones. For example, Livanios (2019) argues against a form of dispositional structuralism based on a *truthmaking principle of dispositionality*, which goes as follows:

The first-order state of affairs of an object instantiating a fundamental dispositional property is by itself (part of) a minimal truthmaker for specific modal truths ('traditionally' expressed by specific non-trivial counterfactuals) which concern the bestowal of specific powers on the object. (Livanios 2019, p. 210)

Accordingly, a symmetry structure is dispositional just in case it is by itself (part of) a minimal truthmaker for specific modal truths. On the identity-based criterion, a symmetry structure (or some other feature) is dispositional just in case its identity is at least partially fixed by its dispositional character.

Why not sticking with the truthmaking principle of dispositionality? There are two main reasons. The first one is that I wish to preserve the focus on the dispositional character rather than

⁶ For a similar idea implemented into quantum mechanics, see Esfeld and Dorato (2010).

modal truths.⁷ The second is that I disagree with Livanios's claim that a definitional trait of a dispositional feature is to provide a metaphysical explanation for laws of nature (2019, p. 211). Of course, a complete dispositionalist theory should accommodate laws of nature in some ways or other. But we are not forced to define dispositional features as truthmakers for laws of nature. This point is important. Let me expand on it.

Livanios maintains that standard dispositionalist views (e.g. Bird 2007) are meant to offer a ground for specific modal truths about the actual world which, among others, include laws of nature. According to Livanios, any dispositionalist should prove that laws of nature "*qua* ontologically derivative, are not indispensable parts of any metaphysical explanation of the modal facts at issue" (Livanios 2019, p. 211). Here I part ways with Livanios.

The truth of dispositionalism should not depend on whether laws of nature can be derived from fundamental dispositional features. The dispositionalist thesis is about the ontological type of fundamental features. It is not a view about the relation between these features and laws of nature. In fairness, Livanios is right in claiming that dispositionalism has been often proposed as a package deal that includes a view about laws of nature. And surely, anti-dispositionalists and law-firsters are right in thinking that any complication with deriving laws from dispositional features represents an objection against the view. However, this derivation is not a necessary requirement for *any form* of dispositionalism. This position only requires that laws of nature do not determine the dispositional character of fundamental features. Thus, someone could adopt a view *a lá* Mumford (2004), who denies the metaphysical robustness of laws of nature. Perhaps this is a radical option, but one which is indeed available. Note that dispositionalism does not banish laws *tout court*.⁸ Rather it commits us to deny that laws are substantive entities that govern the dispositionality of features. Therefore,

⁷ Of course, the dispositional character of a feature comprises a modal element for, on dispositionalism, it is necessarily tied to the dispositional feature in questions. I will discuss Livanios's dispositional structuralism in more detail in Section 3. It is worth noting that someone might expand the notion of dispositionality to include *all* modal truths (e.g. Vetter 2015).

⁸ It is worth acknowledging that Mumford (2004) does embrace a lawlessness picture of the world.

dispositionalism is compatible with approaches that take laws to be suitable generalizations of observed regularities or mere predictive devices that carry no ontological weight. As Bird acknowledges it, dispositionalism implies that laws are regularities that supervene on instantiations of fundamental dispositional properties (2007, pp. 81–82).

Unlike the truthmaking principle, the identity principle of dispositionality is more ecumenical: it is available to dispositionalists of various stripes, who might differ with respect to how they conceive the relation between dispositional features and laws of nature. It also allows us to set aside, at least for the purposes of this paper, the complicated question of how symmetry structures and laws of nature are related.⁹

Now let us clarify the notion of a symmetry structure. I shall follow Livanios (2010, 2019), who takes symmetry structures to be groups of specific transformations that leave invariant certain features of objects (or laws) and are analysed by the mathematical formalism of group theory.¹⁰ An ordinary example will illustrate. Take a vinyl record. If you rotate it about a specific axis, the vinyl retains its shape. Intuitively, a vinyl record is symmetric under rotations. We can distinguish between external and internal symmetries, and global and local symmetries. An external symmetry is one which involves the variation of a spatio-temporal variable. Spatial rotations are examples of external symmetries. An internal symmetry does not alter the spatio-temporal variables. A symmetry is global if it is not a function of a space-time variable. A symmetry is local if it is (for an overview of the concept of symmetry and its philosophical relevance, see Brading and Castellani 2002). I shall

⁹ Livanios (2019) argues against the possibility of deriving *all* laws solely from symmetry structures. If we accept the truthmaking principle of dispositionality, this case undermines dispositional structuralism.

¹⁰ Symmetry transformations satisfy the conditions of forming a group. The latter is defined as a set, G , with a product operation (\bullet) such that for any element a and b of G , $a \bullet b$ belongs to G ; it is associative, namely $a(bc) = (ab)c$ for any a, b, c of G ; it contains the identity element; and for each element of G , there is an inverse.

also assume symmetry structures correspond to physical aspects of reality *out there*, and that physical relational systems, say a pair of particles, can instantiate or realize such structures.¹¹

To clarify this characterisation, let us consider two examples of relevant symmetry structures. First, consider the Poincaré Group, which has primary importance in physics. Wigner (1939) showed that the states of elementary particles transform according to the irreducible representations (sets of states that are mapped into one another by the action of the relevant transformations) of this group. The Poincaré Group is associated with the global external symmetry under the action of Lorentz boosts and rotations, and of space-time translations. Another important symmetry structure is the product group $SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$. This structure underlies the Standard Model of elementary particles and comprises gauge symmetries about the covariance of the fundamental equations of motion for specific interactions. It is not my aim to defend that claim that *this* or *that* symmetry structure is truly fundamental. As such, the following examples are meant to be illustrative only. Recall that my purpose is different: I wish to defend the view that fundamental symmetry structures, irrespective of what these are, can be plausibly regarded as dispositional in accordance with the identity-based criterion of dispositionality.

So far, I clarified how the identity criterion of dispositionality differ from the truthmaking principle and described the notion of a symmetry structure. Now I turn to discuss the Grounded Argument against dispositionalism.

2. The Grounded Argument against Dispositionalism

The Grounded Argument establishes that putative fundamental dispositional properties such as *charge*, *mass*, and *spin*, are grounded in symmetry structures. Therefore, *pace* the dispositionalist, they are not ungrounded.

¹¹ Some ontic structuralist spurn the idea of objects (e.g. Ladyman and Ross 2007). On this eliminative version, symmetry structures are manifested as features of reality that are not realized by objects. Here I am using a loose or liberal notion of an object. In the remainder of the paper, I will ignore this complication.

The Grounded Argument opposes an *Ungrounded Argument* for dispositionalism (Mumford 2006). According to the latter, the fundamental physical properties posited by physics are ungrounded dispositional ones. In its simplest form, we can reconstruct the Ungrounded Argument as follows (Mumford 2006, p. 479):

- (1) There are subatomic particles that are simple.
- (2) That which is simple has no lower-level components or properties.
- (3) The properties of subatomic particles are (all) dispositional.
- (4) The grounds of a dispositional property can be found only among the lower-level components or properties of which it is a property.
- (5) The dispositional properties of subatomic particles have no grounds.
- (6) Therefore, there exist some ungrounded dispositional properties.

In what follows, I shall ignore premises (1) and (2) (of course, the truth of these premises is questionable; see Williams (2009) for a discussion of the Ungrounded Argument). Instead I shall focus on the other premises, which are the ones that the Grounded Argument rejects.

To start, let us agree that if something is ungrounded, then it is fundamental. Thus, the conclusion (6) expresses the dispositional thesis, namely that some fundamental physical properties are dispositional.

Now let us consider (4). A ground of a dispositional property D is something distinct from D by virtue of which a thing instantiates D (e.g. Molnar 2003, p. 125; Mumford 2006, pp. 477–478). More generally, it is something that enables, supports, affords or permits the possession of D by a thing between its manifestation.

Typically, the idea of grounds for dispositional properties is spelled out in terms of their *causal bases* (e.g. Prior, Pargetter, and Jackson 1982). A causal basis is a non-dispositional property that grounds the possession of a dispositional property. On this view, a dispositional property such as *being fragile* is grounded in a non-dispositional property such as *having a certain crystalline structure*. *Being fragile* is dispositional in virtue of the distinct, non-dispositional property of *having*

a certain crystalline structure. The dispositionalist maintains that some fundamental physical properties are dispositional, and nothing grounds them. For example, if the Ungrounded Argument is true, there is no other non-dispositional property by virtue of which an electron has the dispositional property of *having a determinate charge*. To stress the contrast, the causal basis theorist would argue that if this property is dispositional, then it is grounded in some distinct non-dispositional property of the electron in question.¹²

Now let us consider (5), the crucial premise of the Ungrounded Argument. To defend the truth of (5), dispositionalists appeal to scientific practice. For example, Molnar (1999, p. 13) claims that the “in the Standard Model the fundamental physical magnitudes are represented as ones whose nature is exhausted by their dispositionality”. Along similar lines, Mumford says that (5) is supported by “physical theory, not just as it is interpreted by philosophers but also by scientists disinterested in this debate” (2006, p. 475). To support his claim, Mumford considers standard definitions of physical terms such as *charge*, *mass*, and *spin* that can be found in physics dictionary (e.g. Isaacs 2000). *Charge* is defined as the property of some elementary particles that gives rise to an interaction between them. *Mass* is a measure of a body’s inertia which can be also defined in terms of the gravitational force it produces. *Spin* is the part of the total angular moment of a physical object like a particle. In the same spirit, Ellis (2002, p. 47) claims that:

The fundamental properties of physical theory are all dispositional properties of things that have them ...Gravitational mass, for examples, is a causal power: it is the power of an object

¹² For reasons of space, I shall not discuss whether the causal basis view is preferable to dispositionalism. Of course, this view is not exempt from objections. For example, on the causal basis view, the causal and explanatory efficacy of dispositional properties is unclear: if causal bases ground the dispositional character of properties, we could avoid positing dispositional properties. However, if causal bases are the grounds of dispositionality, then it is also mysterious why these should be considered as non-dispositional (e.g. Heil 2003, pp. 87–90).

to generate gravitational fields. Charge is a causal power: it is the power of a body to produce electromagnetic fields. The intrinsic angular momentum, or spin, is the power to contribute to the total angular momentum of a system.¹³

Of course, claims about what physics tells us face difficulties on their own. However, if the dispositionalist were right, premise (5) of the Ungrounded Argument would gain significant traction. We face an immediate question: is the dispositionalist correct in claiming that physics suggests that fundamental physical properties are ungrounded?

Enter the *Grounded* Argument. Livanios (2016, 2019) argues that premise (5) is false on the basis of the very scientific practice that dispositionalists invoke. Dispositionalist are guilty of neglecting that “state-independent fundamental properties can be characterised as invariants under the action of certain fundamental symmetry groups” (Livanios 2016, p. 47). Accordingly, symmetry structures can be plausibly regarded as the grounds of fundamental dispositional properties. We can make the Grounded Argument against dispositionalism more precise as follows:

- (1) Alleged fundamental dispositional properties are grounded in fundamental symmetry structures.
- (2) Fundamental symmetry structures are not dispositional.
- (3) If alleged fundamental dispositional properties are grounded in symmetry structures and symmetry structures are not dispositional, then dispositionalism is false.

From (1) – (3), we reach the conclusion that:

¹³ Some dispositionalists think that all natural properties posited by science are dispositional. As Chakravartty puts it, “according to the dispositional realist, masses, charges, accelerations, chemical valences, volumes, and various other properties of scientific interest can be described in terms of the dispositions of things to behave in certain ways in the presence or absence of other properties” (2017, p. 103).

(4) Dispositionalism is false.

Premise (1) is supported by contemporary physics: fundamental properties can be identified or characterised as *invariants* under the action of the transformations of fundamental symmetry structures.¹⁴ This possibility strongly suggests that fundamental properties are indeed grounded in fundamental symmetry structures: it is in virtue of certain fundamental symmetry structures that certain (allegedly fundamental) physical properties are instantiated. Said in the jargon of (metaphysical) explanation, it is the existence of symmetry structures that accounts for the existence of certain physical properties. I have already introduced the notion of a symmetry structure (Section 1). For the sake of brevity, I shall not repeat it. Instead let us consider two examples that Livianos mentions *against* paradigmatic examples of ungrounded dispositional properties.

Consider *mass* and *spin*. As mentioned earlier, Wigner (1939) showed that the states of elementary particles transform according to irreducible representations of the Poincaré Group.¹⁵ By computing all the irreducible representations of the Poincaré Group, Wigner found that all the representations which satisfy certain physical criteria can be associated with two parameters m and s . In turn, m and s can be identified respectively with the rest mass and spin of particles. In a slightly more precise way, any representation of a continuous group has some operators, which called Casimir operators, that commute with all operators in the representation. The Casimir operators of a specific irreducible representation have fixed numerical values. Therefore, they can be used to characterise the irreducible representation (for a detailed technical treatment, see Hamermesh 1989,

¹⁴ An invariant is a property of a physical system or law that remains unchanged under the action of specific transformations.

¹⁵ A representation of a symmetry group is an action of the group on a vector space such that each member of the groups acts a linear transformation. A representation is irreducible if it contains no proper invariant sub-spaces.

pp. 317–318 and Livanios 2010, pp. 299–300). The Casimir operators of the Poincaré Group are $C_1 = -m^2$ and $C_2 = -m^2s(s+1)$. C_1 identifies mass. C_2 , with the support of C_1 , identifies spin.

Non consider *charge*, another well-liked property among dispositionalists. It has been shown that this property can be derived from the internal continuous symmetry group $U(1)$. The Lagrangian function $L = T - V$, where T is the kinetic energy and V is the potential energy of any massive scalar field ϕ is invariant under the action of the transformations $\phi \rightarrow e^{-i\Lambda}\phi$ and $\phi^* \rightarrow e^{i\Lambda}\phi^*$ (where Λ is a constant, and ϕ^* is complex conjugate of the field ϕ) that are associated with $U(1)$ (for technical details, see Livanios 2010, p. 300).

The possibility of identifying *mass*, *spin*, and *charge* via symmetry-based considerations strongly suggests that the corresponding symmetry structures are the grounds of these properties. Note that premise (1) of the Grounded Argument does not threaten the claim that these physical properties are dispositional. Rather it undermines the claim that they are ungrounded.

Now let us consider (2). To support this premise, Livanios argues that not all symmetry structures can satisfy *his* truthmaking principle of dispositionality (2019, p. 210; for a formulation of the principle, see Section 1). As I explained in the previous section, Livanios takes that a consequence of the truthmaking principle is that if symmetry structures are dispositional, then they should determine the associated laws of nature (2019, pp. 210–211). Therefore, by *modus tollens*, if a symmetry structure does not determine the associated laws of nature, then it is not dispositional. Livanios illustrates this claim by considering the Local Gauge Hypothesis. To avoid complicating matters without necessity, I will be brief and sketchy (see Livanios 2019, pp. 212–214 for the relevant technicalities).

Suppose to adopt the Local Gauge Hypothesis, which states that the form of dynamical laws of the fundamental interactions is *exclusively* determined by local gauge symmetries. Now consider an interaction-free matter charged field whose action is invariant under the localised phase symmetry transformations associated with $U(1)$. In order to permit the truth of the Hypothesis, one must modify the relevant Lagrangian and render it invariant. This modification requires us to invoke gauge potentials that describe a form of coupling of the matter field to a new field. Only such an amended Lagrangian, which preserves invariance under the local transformations, could allow us

to derive the associated dynamical laws (in this case, the laws are those of electromagnetic interaction). However, it has been shown that local gauge invariance does not “by itself and uniquely determines the dynamical laws” (Livanios 2019, p. 212; for technical details, see Brown 1999 and Martin 2002). To secure the invariance of the Lagrangian, we need to invoke gauge potentials. As it happens, the choice of gauge potentials appears to depend on independent factors such as simplicity and renormalizability. The case generalizes: it appears that local gauge symmetries *on their own* do not ground the derivation of laws. Therefore, Livanios contends, these symmetry structures do not satisfy the truthmaking principle of dispositionality.

A dispositionalist could demur the generality of the above case for it does not show that *all symmetry structures* are non-dispositional.¹⁶ Livanios acknowledges this point. For instance, he notes that conservation laws can be suitably regarded as derivable from continuous global symmetries (as stated by Noether’s first theorem). Yet the problem remains: not every structure is dispositional. As Livanios puts it:

Even a dispositional structuralist who claims that *only some* symmetry structures are dispositional should admit something that undermines her view; namely that there exist a second fundamental source of modality in the actual world besides inherently modal structures. (2019, p. 215)

If physics tells us that laws cannot be uniquely derived from symmetry structures, and *if we adopt the truthmaking principle of dispositionality*, then it is bad news for dispositionalism. The Grounded Argument undermines the dispositionalist thesis: not all fundamental symmetry structures are dispositional. This result pierces the heart of the dispositionalist doctrine for it denies that fundamental features of reality are dispositional.

¹⁶ Someone could attempt to resist Livanios’s case by appealing to physics. I do not wish to pursue this strategy here. Nor do I possess the competence for attempting it.

Perhaps some dispositionalists would be happy with the view that only some symmetry structures are dispositional. But the resigned acceptance of this view is too quick. Is there any strategy for resisting the Grounded Argument?

In what follows, I will defend a positive answer to this question. I will argue that the dispositionalist should embrace a *moderate dispositional structuralism*, the view that fundamental symmetry structures are dispositional although not exhaustively so (more on the ‘moderate’ qualification in Section 3). It is important to acknowledge that this is not the same view that Livanios (2019) discusses. The crucial step for articulating the proposed version of dispositional structuralism is to abandon the truthmaking principle of dispositionality. This principle plays an essential role in Livanios’s defence of premise (2) of the Grounded Argument. However, I have already argued that dispositionalists are not forced to define the dispositional in terms of ground for laws of nature (Section 1). Moreover, the very problems that arise in attempting to derive laws of nature from symmetry structures should give the dispositionalist some compelling reasons for favouring another principle of dispositionality. By adopting the identity-based criterion of dispositionality (Section 1), which states that a feature is dispositional just in case its identity is at least partially fixed by its dispositional character, the dispositionality of symmetry structures does not hang on the derivation of laws. Therefore, the fact that laws cannot be derived uniquely from symmetry structures does not jeopardize their dispositionality.

It seems to me that the adoption of the identity-based version of moderate dispositional structuralism is the most promising way to resist the Grounded Argument. Dispositionalists who reject premise (1) burden themselves with task of arguing against symmetry-based approaches in physics. Such a strategy would go against the very spirit of articulating a metaphysics that is also scientifically-informed. It is therefore a non-starter.

I devote the remainder of this paper to illustrate *moderate dispositional structuralism* and its merits (and drawbacks). Along the way, I discuss the prospects of a stronger, more radical form of dispositional structuralism. However, as it will become clear in due course, these are rather dim. My conclusion will be that the dispositionalist should rest content with the moderate version, which still captures the central tenet of dispositionalism.

3. Moderate Dispositional Structuralism

Moderate dispositional structuralism is the view that fundamental symmetry structures are dispositional although not exhaustively so. Here dispositionality should be understood in accordance with the identity-based criterion (Section 1). Accordingly, a symmetry structure is dispositional just in case its identity is at least partially fixed by its dispositional character—namely, it is at least partially determined by its causal/nomic/dispositional roles. If it is plausible to maintain that fundamental symmetry structures are dispositional, then the Grounded Argument does not undermine the dispositionalist thesis that the fundamental features are dispositional. Nor should the dispositionalist abandon their view *because* of the impossibility of deriving laws of nature *solely* from symmetry structures. Now I turn to explain how symmetry structures can be plausibly regarded as dispositional. After that, I justify why the emerging form of dispositional structuralism is moderate. For now, let us set this qualification aside.

To start, let us stress the difference between *this* version of dispositional structuralism and Livanios's (2019). On Livanios's truthmaking principle of dispositionality, dispositional structuralism is the view that fundamental symmetry structures are minimal truthmakers for modal truths, which include laws of nature. Livanios takes that a consequence of this principle is that symmetry structures should permit the derivation of the relevant laws. However, contemporary physics shows that such a derivation is not possible. Therefore, the truthmaking version of dispositional structuralism fails to secure the dispositionalist thesis. By contrast, on the identity-based criterion of dispositionality, a symmetry structure can be dispositional and yet fail to ground *on its own* the derivation of laws of nature.¹⁷ Of course, dispositionalism should be compatible with

¹⁷ Note that any dispositionalist approach that accepts laws of nature as metaphysically substantive entities faces an inescapable tension. Either laws of nature are grounded in fundamental dispositional entities and are thus not substantive or they are substantive but not grounded in fundamental dispositional entities. As I argued in Section 1, the dispositionalist is not obliged to accept the substantivity of laws (e.g. Mumford 2004). For example, the dispositionalist could maintain that

the view certain laws can be derived partially or fully from symmetry structures. Fortunately, the *identity-based version* of dispositional structuralism ticks this box. On this view, the identity of a symmetry structure can be partially fixed by its dispositional character *and* partially by its role of grounding the derivation (partial or full) of associated laws. Said differently, the dispositional structuralist can maintain that a symmetry structure is dispositional *and* plays the role of grounding (partially or fully) certain laws.

Now the task is to show that the identity of fundamental symmetry structures is indeed partially fixed by their dispositional character. Roughly put, the dispositional structuralist should make the case that the identity of a symmetry structure is determined at least in part by what it does *causally/nomically/dispositionally speaking*. Recall that the dispositional character includes causal/nomic/dispositional roles, which are causal/nomic/dispositional relations that a feature bears to other ones (Bird 2016). Is it outrageously outlandish to hold that fundamental symmetry structures play some causal/nomic/dispositional roles? It does not seem so.¹⁸

Consider the first the nomic role of symmetry structures. Plausibly, something plays a nomic role if it is involved in laws of nature. Here the dispositional structuralist can hold that symmetry structures play a nomic role for they permit the partial or full derivation of certain laws. For example, one could argue that since we can derive conservation laws from global and local gauge symmetries via Noether's theorem, these symmetries play a nomic role. Livanios (2019) points out that this strategy does not show that gauge symmetries *on their own* permit the derivation of laws (as in the case of local gauge symmetries and fundamental interaction laws). Yet this

laws of nature are suitable systematic generalizations from observed regularities among dispositional entities. Humean accounts of laws of nature embrace a similar ontologically innocent conception of laws of nature (e.g. Lewis 1973, 1983).

¹⁸ Arguably, symmetry structures do not play a causal role in the sense of *producing certain effects*. A more plausible understanding of the causal role of symmetry structures is that they ground counterfactual dependencies that involve physical properties and laws (e.g. Lange 2007; French 2014). However, this conception falls broadly within the nomic role of symmetry structures.

limitation is not a problem for the dispositional structuralist who embraces the identity-based criterion of dispositionality. It suffices that the identity of symmetry structures is partially fixed by the nomic role of grounding, partially or fully, the derivation of certain laws. Another way in which symmetry structures are involved in laws is by dictating their regularity or constraining certain parameters. An example would be the role of continuous symmetries in grounding conservation laws.

Perhaps an opponent could argue that symmetry structures do not necessitate their nomic roles. In the spirit of dispositionalism, the dispositional structuralist would reject this claim: every fundamental symmetry structure necessitates certain nomic roles.¹⁹ One way to motivate the necessity would be to block implausible scenarios in which the same symmetry structure plays different nomic roles. Arguably, the anti-Humean would not find these cases problematic. But the dispositional structuralist would insist that the acceptance of such cases implies that the identity of a symmetry structure is *quidditistically* fixed: since the same symmetry structure S could play distinct nomic roles in different possible worlds, the identity of S is independent from them. Here the dispositional structuralist could invoke some standard objections against quidditism (for an overview, see Bird 2007, pp. 70–76). A pressing one applied to the case of empirically significant symmetry structures is that quidditism would leave us in the dark about their identity. What we know about symmetry structures that are relevant in physics is constrained by their nomic role. But if the identity of symmetry structures is independent from their nomic role, then we are seemingly fated to remain ignorant. The dispositional structuralist evades this problem for they take the identity of symmetry structures to be fixed by their necessary nomic role. Once we know the nomic role of a symmetry structure, we also know its identity.

So much for the nomic role of symmetry structure. Now let us consider their dispositional role. The dispositional structuralist could argue that “being invariant under the action of specific

¹⁹ Note that the claim is that a symmetry structure S necessitates a nomic role N. Accordingly, in every possible world where S and N exist, S plays N. This claim should not be confused with the one that S and N are necessary. As Lange (2007) argues, symmetry structures can be involved in laws of nature, thereby playing a nomic role, despite these being different from the actual ones.

transformations” is a disposition, and that reference to such a disposition is necessary to identify (at least partially) symmetry structures. One way to argue that symmetry structures play this role is to consider that they are associated with specific transformations that yield invariants (those properties of a physical systems that remain unchanged under the action of certain transformations).²⁰

There is widespread agreement that dispositions cannot be specified independently from (non-trivial) counterfactuals that appeal to manifestations and circumstances.²¹ Invariance under specific transformations appears to be suitable for such a characterisation. We could say that some x has the disposition to remain unchanged in some respects P under certain transformation T of a symmetry group because if x were under the action of T , then x would manifest P . Arguably, the manifestation P is an invariant feature denoted by a quantity. An objector might argue that there is something odd in a disposition whose manifestation is to leave something unaltered. But many dispositions do so. A familiar example is elasticity, which is the disposition of a thing to resist a distorting force and return to its original size and shape. Another example is waterproofing. A waterproof object has the disposition to remain unaffected by the infiltration of water. The charge of oddity does not jeopardize the plausibility of regarding invariance as a disposition. This characterisation captures the sense that invariance under the action of symmetry transformations involves the comparison of specific quantities (that correspond to physical properties) in various possible circumstances. To assess whether something is invariant, we need to verify whether it interacts in the same way before and after certain transformations.

²⁰ I am restricting my attention to the claim that symmetry structures are dispositional. This should not be confused with the claim that *all* structures are dispositional.

²¹ Note that here the claim is not that dispositions are adequately analysed in these terms. The task of providing a healthy conditional analysis of dispositions is notoriously difficult. Here the claim is that the dispositional character of dispositional features is standardly specified in terms of manifestations in certain circumstances. Even dispositionalists who think that dispositions should not be reduced to counterfactual conditionals should agree with this claim.

The dispositional structuralist has to show that every symmetry structure is partially identified by this dispositional role. One way to accomplish this aim is to argue that current physical practice corroborates this claim. Symmetry structures, in fact, can be identified by specific transformations and the features that are left unchanged (Livanios 2010, p. 299). To bridge the gap between physics and metaphysics, the dispositional structuralist could maintain that being associated with specific transformations that yield certain invariants is a part of what makes the case that something is a symmetry structure. Therefore, we might reasonably infer that symmetry structures necessitate their dispositional role. Accordingly, in every possible world, for every symmetry structure S and for every associated dispositional role D to yield invariants under specific transformations, if S exists, then S plays D . By adopting this view, we block worrisome Humean scenarios where S plays D in a possible world and D^* in another one.

Let me illustrate the proposal with two examples (for a more technical treatment, see any good textbook of physics or Morrison 1995). Take *mass* and *spin*. Recall that they can be characterised as invariants under the action of transformations associated with the Poincaré Group. On dispositional structuralism, the Poincaré Group is dispositional because its identity is partially fixed by the associated disposition to leave *mass* and *spin* invariant under the action of Lorentz boosts and rotations, and of space-time translations. Now consider *charge*, which can be characterised via symmetry-based considerations that involve the group $U(1)$. On dispositional structuralism, $U(1)$ is dispositional because its identity is partially fixed by the associated disposition of any massive scalar field φ to remain unchanged with respect to the Lagrangian function $L = T - V$ (where T and V are the kinetic and potential energy respectively) under the action of the transformations $\varphi \rightarrow e^{-i\Lambda}\varphi$ and $\varphi^* \rightarrow e^{i\Lambda}\varphi^*$ (where Λ is a constant and φ^* is complex conjugate of the field φ). The dispositional structuralist would contend that every fundamental symmetry structure is dispositional in the sense that its identity is partially fixed by a certain dispositional role. Fairly obviously, it is better to leave to physicists the task of finding which features are invariants under which transformations.

Putting these pieces together, we get an identity-based version of dispositional structuralism. It is a version of dispositionalism because it takes the fundamental features of reality

to be partially identified by their dispositional character which comprises the nomic and dispositional roles of symmetry structures. It is a form of structuralism because it maintains that the fundamental entities are symmetry structures as investigated by contemporary physics.

Now it is time to explain why the version of dispositional structuralism outlined so far is moderate. Suppose you are convinced that it is plausible to think of the identity of the identity of symmetry structures as partially fixed by their nomic and dispositional roles. We might ask: is there more to the identity of symmetry structures? The *moderate* dispositional structuralist says “yes”. On this view, symmetry structures have a *non-dispositional character* in addition to their dispositional one, which is captured by their nomic and dispositional roles they play.

Moderate dispositional structuralism denies that dispositionality is all there is to symmetry structure. Therefore, it is in stark contrast with the *radical* version of dispositionalism according to which the dispositional character of dispositional features “exhaust their being” (Bird 2007, p. 100). In the literature, radical dispositionalism, which also goes under the name of the *pure powers* view, has been presented as a view about properties (e.g. Mumford 2004; Bird 2007; Taylor 2018). On this view, properties are “nothing more than a set of connections to, and causal powers for, other properties” (Mumford 2004, p. 185). Granted that we can extend this “nothing more” claim to symmetry structures, can someone hold that symmetry structures are *exhaustively* or *purely* dispositional? It seems to me that this view has yet to garner its plausibility.

It is hard to deny that fundamental symmetry structures are largely characterised mathematically in accordance with group theory. Many of their features do not seem amenable to a dispositional characterisation. Said differently, we can specify many aspects of symmetry structures independently from any dispositions. For example, a symmetry structure can be Abelian or not, finite or infinite, continuous or discrete, and so on. These are mathematical descriptions that refer to non-dispositional features of symmetry structures: they concern the elements of symmetry structures and their organization. The moderate dispositional structuralist holds that these non-dispositional features partially fix the identity of symmetry structures. The radical dispositional structuralist, who denies this claim, should argue for the implausible view that *every feature* of a symmetry structure

is dispositional. This strikes me as implausible. Take the Poincaré Group, which is non-Abelian.²² This means that the Poincaré Group is non-commutative: there is at least a pair of members of this group such that $a \bullet b \neq b \bullet a$ (an Abelian group, such as $U(1)$, is commutative; \bullet is a binary operation). This property is evidently non-dispositional: we can specify being non-commutative independently from any dispositional or causal or nomic role. The same reasoning applies to the other mathematical descriptions of a symmetry structure that capture the relations between its elements in non-dispositional ways.

An immediate question arises: does the fact that symmetry structures have non-dispositional features threaten *moderate* dispositional structuralism? The answer is negative. The moderate version is compatible with the possibility that the identity of a symmetry structure is partially determined by its dispositional character *and*, partially, by its non-dispositional one, which comprise those mathematical features that cannot be characterised dispositionally. For instance, the moderate structuralist can maintain that $U(1)$ is dispositional because it is partially identified by the associated disposition of any massive scalar field to remain unchanged with respect to the Lagrangian function $L = T - V$ under the action of specific transformations. Yet $U(1)$ is also partially identified by its mathematical features such as that of being Abelian and being continuous (i.e. its elements are labelled by continuous variables, say (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r) , where each variable has a well-defined range). On moderate dispositional structuralism, the *full* identification of a symmetry structure involves both its dispositional *and* non-dispositional character. The emerging view is a form of dispositionalism that does not deny the existence of non-dispositional features that symmetry structures have. Crucially, the acceptance of non-dispositional features of symmetry structures is what makes moderate dispositional structuralism a more plausible view.

²² In addition to commutativity, an Abelian group must satisfy other properties that appear to be non-dispositional: (i) associativity: for any x, y, z of a group G , $(x \bullet y) \bullet z = x \bullet (y \bullet z)$; (ii) it has an identity element e such that $e \bullet x = x \bullet e = x$ for any $x \in G$; for any x , there is an inverse of x such that there exist a $y \in G$ such that $x \bullet y = e = y \bullet x$; (iii) closure: for any $x, y \in G$, $x \bullet y$ is in G .

Before concluding, it is important to stress that the acceptance of non-dispositional features of symmetry structures do not clash with scientific practice. Namely, they are not odd metaphysically extras that lack empirical relevance. Simply, these are features of symmetry structures that are not amenable to a dispositional characterisation such as those described by certain mathematical predicates (e.g. “being Abelian”). But these features are needed to provide a complete account of symmetry structures. Moderate dispositional structuralism is therefore the structuralist analogous of *aspect views* of properties, according to which these have dispositional and non-dispositional parts that jointly together characterise them fully (e.g. Martin and Heil 1999; Hawthorne 2001; Taylor 2018; Williams 2019; Giannotti forthcoming).²³

To wrap up, dispositionalists often appeal to physics to support the thesis that all fundamental physical properties are ungrounded dispositions. However, contemporary physics undermines this thesis. Putative fundamental properties such as *mass*, *charge*, and *spin* can be plausibly regarded as grounded in fundamental symmetry structures. Livanios (2019) argues against the view that symmetry structures are dispositional because the former do not fully ground the derivation of the latter. Here I argued that if we adopt the identity-based criterion of dispositionality, we can articulate a moderate form of dispositional structuralism that does not demand the derivation of laws from symmetry structures. Along the way, I discussed the dim prospects of a radical version of dispositional structuralism. My conclusion is that the dispositional structuralist should rest content with the moderate version. After all, this view captures the spirit of the dispositionalist doctrine: although not exhaustively so, the fundamental symmetry structures are dispositional. Here I have done nothing more than defending the general plausibility of moderate dispositional structuralism. But this suffices to pave the way to a more scientifically-responsible form of dispositionalism. My hope is that other dispositionalists will follow this trend.

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²³ The version of moderate dispositional structuralism outlined here should not be confused with the view that Hawthorne (200) labels *modest causal structuralism*.

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